

ANALYSIS OF JOINTS IN PULTRUDED COMPOSITE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

The general behaviour of mechanically fastened joints can be discussed under three broad headings: fastener type; materials; geometric factors.

Pultruded composite beams present an outstanding behavior under tension loads. The critical point is the joints between two or more pultruded beams.

In this work, a study of mechanical joints of pultruded composite beams is carried out. Graphics of efficiency in function of different geometric and material parameters are presented.

Mechanical fasteners and bolted joints are analyzed and conclusions of the experimental study are presented.

Although mechanically fastened joints in pultruded composite beams exhibit the same failure modes as in metals, the mechanisms by which damage initiates and propagates is fundamentally different and extremely complex. The dependence of damage development and associated strength on through-thickness restraint means that torque-tightened bolts are superior to rivets which, in turn, are superior to other forms of mechanical fastening.

The influence on failure of the relative values of fibre and matrix failure strain explains, in part, the strength differences between CFRP (carbon or graphite fibre-reinforced epoxy resin), GFRP (glass fibre-reinforced epoxy), KFRP ("Kevlar" fibre-reinforced epoxy), and GRP (glass fibre-reinforced polyester resin). Lay-up and stacking sequence are also important since they determine the stress distribution around the fastener hole.

Joint behaviour, and particularly the failure mode, is also dependent on joint geometry, i. e. width in single-hole joints or pitch in multi-hole joints; end (or edge) distance; hole diameter; laminate thickness.

In addition to the above, joint performance is also determined by several other factors including: hole quality; the fit of the fastener in the hole (i. e. the relative diameters of fastener and hole); and the fit of the fastener in the washer (for bolted joints). The latter effect can be particularly important in fatigue.

KEYWORDS: Joint; Tensile; Shear; Bearing; Failure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The design methods that have been established for structural joints in metals are applicable, in a general fashion, to fiberglass composites.

However, as is to be expected, the physical nature of fiberglass composites does introduce problems that are not encountered with metals, and, although trends can be established, it is usually not possible to "read across" from one composite system to another. The anisotropic stiffness and strength, the low interlaminar shear, and through-thickness tensile strengths mean that unexpected failure modes may be introduced.

The behavior of the joint could also be influenced by the fiber type and form (random mat, woven fabric, unidirectional, etc.), resin type and fiber volume fraction. In addition the strength of the joint is determined by the joint type (single or double lap, etc.) and geometry, bolt size, washer size, clamping force, hole size and tolerance. Of all these parameters the clamping force, namely the force in the through-thickness direction caused by tightening the bolt, is of critical importance.

Three basic failure modes, can be identified (Figures 1, 2, 3). Ideally, one would like the corresponding failure loads to occur at the same load. If this is not possible, bearing failure is preferred, if only because this mode is not catastrophic. However, this may not produce the lightest joint.

In Figure 4, the relation between these three failure modes and the ratio d/w is represented.

Figure 1. Bearing failure

Figure 2. Shear failure

Figure 3. Tension failure

Figure 4. Failure modes in pultruded fiberglass E/polyester composites.

In Figure 4, efficiency versus d/w for a fiberglass composite and the three types of failure modes associated to typical d/w ratios are represented.

For reasons of cost and convenience, basic experimental data is usually obtained from single bolt specimens, loaded in double shear, with the geometry shown in Figure 5. Stresses are defined in terms of the failure load, normally taken as the maximum tensile load sustained by the joint. Geometrical variables are described in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Definition of variables

2. DESCRIPTION OF TESTING

The aim of the testing is to analyze the behavior of joints in pultruded composite materials.

* The type of testing is double shear(figure 5).

* The material used is fiberglass E / polyester resin, the manufacturing process being pultrusion.

* Specimen thickness is 6.5 mm.

* The joint efficiency has been determined by means of the following expression :

$$\epsilon = Q / (\sigma t w)$$

Being:

ϵ : efficiency

Q : joint ultimate tensile strength

σ : ultimate tensile strength in the specimen without hole

t : joint thickness

w : joint width at the net section

* The following parameters have been analyzed :

* d/w (0.3 to 0.8)

* e/w (0.3 to 0.8)

* Torque-tightened bolts (40 to 80 N m)

* Number of washers (0 to 2)

3. TESTING RESULTS

The material used for this testing, showed the following engineering constants and failure parameters :

$$E_1 = 33.093 \text{ GPa}$$

$$E_2 = 8.043 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.25$$

$$G_{12} = 3.986 \text{ GPa}$$

$$X = 658.5 \text{ MPa}$$

$$X' = 591.7 \text{ MPa}$$

$$Y = 29.6 \text{ MPa}$$

$$Y' = 105.2 \text{ MPa}$$

$$S = 71.3 \text{ MPa}$$

Testing results are presented in figures 6 to 10. Efficiency is represented versus d/w for different torque-tightened bolts (40, 60 and 80 N m) in Figures 6 to 8 respectively. In these three graphics, d/t = 1.53 and e/d = 5. The highest efficiency is obtained in the joint without washers and lower values are got in joints with one and two washers.

Efficiency is represented versus e/d for different torque-tightened bolts (40, 60 and 80 N m) and zero and one washer in Figures 9 to 10, respectively. In these two graphics, the ratio d/w = 0.5 and the ratio d/t = 1.53. The highest efficiency is obtained in joints with high torque-tightened bolts (80 N m) and lower values are got for lower torque-tightened bolts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn in the present study are the following :

- 1) The failure modes observed are shear, bearing and tension.
- 2) The ratio d/w is very important. The final results are function of this parameter (Figures 6 to 8).
- 3) The ratio e/w is also critical for getting the optimum design (Figures 9 to 10).
- 4) The optimum efficiency obtained is around 50 %. This value is considered low but still it is interesting because of the high tensile strength measured in pultruded composite materials made by pultrusion processes.
- 5) For this manufacturing process and material, the optima conditions are :
 - Maximum torque
 - No washers.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 6. Efficiency versus d/w for a pultruded fiberglass composite specimen; $e/d = 5$. $T = 40$ N m.

Figure 7. Efficiency versus d/w for a pultruded fiberglass composite specimen; $d/t = 1.53$; $e/d = 5$; $T = 60$ N m.

Figure 8. Efficiency versus d/w for a pultruded fiberglass composite specimen; $d/t = 1.53$; $e/d = 5$; $T = 60 \text{ N m}$.

Figure 9. Efficiency versus e/d for a pultruded fiberglass composite specimen; $d/t = 1.53$; $d/w = 0.5$; No washers.

Figure 10. Efficiency versus e/d for a pultruded fiberglass composite specimen;
 $d/t = 1.53$; $d/w = 0.5$; One washer.

